

**THE DILEMMA OF OFF-CAMPUS ACCOMMODATION AMONG STUDENTS OF
UNIVERSITY OF JOS: IMPLICATIONS FOR CAMPUS HOSTEL MANAGEMENT**

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Abstract

Inadequate hostels in tertiary institutions creates force choice between on-campus and off-campus residence. Students that cannot access on-campus hostels, reside off-campus. Residing off-campus exposes students to kidnaping and death from incessant crisis of which students have fallen victims. In view of these problems, this study is undertaken to ascertain students' choice of residence, identify influencers of students' choice of residence and measures of encouraging on-campus residence. The research findings shown that 45.6% of the students reside on-campus while 54.4% reside off-campus. 46.7% preferred on-campus residence and 53.3% preferred off-campus residence. Major reasons for the preference of on-campus residence are easy access to institution's facilities, availability of water and electricity, low cost of accommodation while privacy, comfort and convenience are for off-campus residence. Topmost influencers are security, hygiene, quality facilities and services, proximity to lecture venue. 'Avoiding leaving accommodation every session' is found as new influencer, constituting an addition to knowledge. Topmost measures for making on-campus residence preferable are regular water and electricity supply, security, hostels renovation, effective management and maintenance practice.

Keywords: students' hostel, on-campus, off-campus, choice

1.0 Introduction

Accommodation is a vital component of tertiary institutions because most of the students live far from where institutions are situated. In order to meet students' accommodation need, institutions necessarily provide or arrange hostels for their students on campus (Wong & Wei-Jie, 2022). Residing on-campus afford students some advantages. On the basis of this submission, Musa et al. (2021) opined that hostel facilities support students' intellectual capabilities. In the same vein, Ghani and Suleiman (2016) posited that, residing on-campus give students the advantages of living in close proximity to faculty at low cost, safety, access to academic support facilities, and enhanced social integration and personal development. Moreover, residing on-campus hostels encourages more engagement in collaborative learning, discussions and interactions that evokes more

commitment to studies (Graham et al., 2018). On-campus residence promotes students' participation in extra-curricular activities such as sports, games, and social activities that enhance their general wellness in ways that living off-campus may not (Yakub & Zaid, 2017).

Advantages accruing from on-campus residence makes residing on campus students' preference. Study by Nwanekezie and Mendie (2019), revealed that, most students prefer on-campus residence to off-campus residence in order to reduce cost and possible distractions from studies. However, increasing students' enrollment into tertiary institutions, especially in public institutions, without commensurate additional hostels space and supporting facilities, has led to higher demand for hostel accommodations (Kamal et al., 2019). Consequently, there is increasing competition for the limited available accommodation. Invariably, not every student that desires on-campus residence gets it. In this circumstance, majority of students have to live off-campus against their wish (Kolawole & Boluwatife, 2016). Furthermore, institutions on wanting to meet accommodation need in the face of limited space, allocate greater number of students than the carrying capacity of rooms, therefore, posing the problem of overcrowding (Ibrahim & Musa, 2017). Overcrowding of accommodation creates problems of lack of privacy, over use of facilities with attendant consequences of faster break down of fittings and facilities, requiring frequent maintenance which can result high maintenance cost (Subair & Adeniyi, 2021; Wahedy & Alim, 2022). High maintenance cost with inadequate fund, makes routine maintenance difficult to effect, consequently, most hostels accommodations are in deplorable state. In the light of these problems, some students are not comfortable with on-campus residence, thereby forced to opt for off-campus residence. As a result, students' have a forced choice of residing on-campus or off-campus. On-campus residence is accommodation situated in the premises of institution of learning to provide living space, and ease utilisation of educational facilities for students at a cost (Ghani & Suleman, 2016; Philip et al., 2018). Off-campus residence on the other hand is accommodation situated outside the premises of institutions that is in the form of apartment suite, semi-segregated, or a solitary abode (Sen & Antara, 2018). Living in any of these places of residence by students are influenced by certain factors.

According to Mahama et al. (2016), students' choice of residence is influenced by factors like accommodation charges, security, water and electricity supply, proximity to lecture halls, and privacy. Kolawole and Boluwatife (2016) are of the notion that proximity to campus, rental value, type of dwelling and facilities provided are the most important factors influencing students' choice of residence. In addition to these submissions, Kobue et al. (2017) included factors like residence location, security, availability of laundry room, internet service, secure parking space, architectural design, computer labs and gymnasium, number of occupants per room, recommendation by others, and unavailability of on-campus accommodation among influencers of students' residence choice. Tuan (2018), identified that the influencers are inclusive of location, facilities, security, rent, quality service and living environment. Taking into cognizance findings of the highlighted researchers, it can be observed that factors influencing students' choice of residence across institutions or countries varies. By implication influencers of students' choice of residence in University of Jos may differ from those identified in literature. Also, review of literature shown that there is no published research on influencers of students' choice of residence as well as measures that can be employed to make on-campus residence students' preference. Hence, there exists knowledge gap in this respect. Furthermore, sizable number of the students' population live off-campus, in view of the incidences of kidnapping and religious crisis of which students have fallen victims, living off-campus exposes the students to dangers. Consequently, this study is

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undertaken to assess the influencers of students' choice of residence with the view to identify measures that can be taken to make on-campus residence preferable.

The study is considered important guide to administrators of tertiary institutions and hostels facilities providers, detailing information on the types of hostel accommodations, facilities and services that meet students' preference as well as strategies to employ in ensuring that adequate accommodations with decent facilities and services are provided for students. Furthermore, it will serve as a guide for the delivery of adequate students' hostel, and provide useful information for viability study on hostels investment.

2.0 Literature Review

2.1 Concept of Students' Hostel and Residence

There are various constructs with regard to students' hostel. According to Dye (2023), students' hostel is a lodging facility designed to eliminate some financial burden from students. It is a vital part of facilities provided by management of tertiary institutions to support students' intellectual efficiency (Musa et al., 2021). Philip et al. (2018), perceived it as an affordable place of residence provided for students to aid access to educational facilities with ease and less distraction. It is also viewed as a place of dwelling for students within an institution's premises with shared facilities like living spaces, common areas, bathrooms, kitchen, etc., for a short term (Yakub & Zaid, 2017). Similarly, it is seen as accommodation situated within educational institution to provide comfort and safety, that allows students feel the impact of school environment on their learning activities (Chiguvi & Ndoma, 2018). The different constructs of students' hostel projects it as integral to students' study and social lives. In agreement with this assertion, Odefadehen et al. (2022), opined that availability of hostel accommodation constitutes a major item of consideration by prospective students in making choice of tertiary institution. The primary reason for students' hostel is to administer positive academic environment through creating a desirable education and social interaction (Subair & Adeniyi, 2021). This implies that administrators of institutions of education are mandated to mobilize the needed resources to make adequate accommodation and facilities available for students. In view the highlighted concepts, this study conceptualized on-campus hostel as affordable accommodations situated within the premises of educational institutions to secure students, and facilitate their academic excellence and social wellbeing. While, off-campus hostels are accommodations provided by private individuals or organisations for students outside the premises of educational institutions.

Students' residence is diversely defined by Scholars. The perception of students' residence by Ghani and Suleiman (2016), means housing units where students reside during their study that is usually away from their parents' dictation. From the standpoint of Adama et al. (2018), it is an abode for students during the term of their academic year. Students' residence is equipped with facilities like bed, bathrooms and toilets, kitchens, recreational areas, laundry rooms, and services such as regular water and electricity supply, maintenance of environment, cafeteria services, internet access among others, to enhance learning experience (Ibrahim & Musa, 2017). According to Akinpelu (2015), students' residential environment motivates academic work through engagement in social and economic activities. The residences are designed as self-contained or shared housing units (Franz & Grube, 2022). They are located either on-campus or off-campus and can be owned and managed by the institution, private entities, or in partnership (Ibrahim et al.,

2019). Consequently, students' residence is grouped into three, namely: institution owned residence, private owned residence, and personal/own residence.

Institution owned residence according to McCann et al. (2020), are accommodations owned and operated by the institution of learning, and can be located either on-campus or off-campus, but very close to the institution. In other words, institution's owned residence can be located on-campus or off-campus. Private owned residence is residence owned by private organisations or individuals rented to students with the sole aim of maximizing profits (Tumer et al., 2019; McCann et al., 2020). The profit maximization drive of private owned residence makes the rent usually higher than the institution owned residence (Ibrahim & Musa, 2017). Personal/own residence is accommodation that is not owned or managed by the institution but are rather privately-owned residence rented to students or owned by students or their relatives. In the view of Abdul-Razak et al. (2017) and Adama et al. (2018), students' residence can either be on-campus or off-campus residence. Similarly, Ogwuchi and Pinga (2017) stated that students that live with their parents, relatives or in a rented private apartment all stay off-campus as long as the residence is located outside the premises of the institution. Hence, for the purpose of this study students' residence is considered in two fronts: on-campus and off-campus residence.

On-campus residence is a place where students live, study, entertain and socialize with other students which is located within the institution's premises (Wong & Wei-Jie, 2022). To Adama et al. (2018), on-campus residence are halls of residence located within institution's premises, and made available to students for sustainability. Philip et al. (2018), explained it as place of residence for students at low-cost, built to facilitate ease to utilisation of educational facilities. As such, students residing on-campus have benefits of full participation in activities of the institution and enjoy the comfort of available hostel facilities (Abdul Razak et al., 2017). Enabling students to develop sense of independence and ability to mingle and bond with fellow students and effective work life (Subair & Adeniyi, 2021; Wong & Wei-Jie, 2022). Moreover, aiding collaborative learning, participation in diverse group discussions and learning programmes, access to institution's resources, and participation in extracurricular activities which are of academic gains (Graham, 2018). However, literature noted that there are challenges attributed to on-campus residence as a result of overcrowding and congestion of shared facilities due to high students' enrollments (Ogunyemi, 2022). The challenges generate problems of irregular water and electricity supply, overstretched use of facilities (Subair & Adeniyi, 2021), poor ventilation, lack of privacy, inadequate availability of facilities, lag in routine maintenance work and repairs, and unhealthy environment, thereby making off-campus residence unattractive to some students (Spio-Kwofie et al., 2016; Ibrahim & Musa, 2017).

Off-campus residence are private hostels where students lodge in exchange of a fee (Adama et al., 2018). It is a privately-owned residence which is either private apartment or an individual home located outside institution's premises given to students on rental basis (Devi et al., 2015; Ghani & Suleiman, 2016). Living off-campus according to Devi et al. (2015), has some advantages as it provides home-like environment which gives students privacy and the opportunity to choose roommate if they so wish. However, the disadvantages of living off-campus include high rents, insecurity, and lateness to lectures due to poor transportation networks and distance, transportation cost, lack of basic facilities (Agava et al., 2018). Furthermore, Ogwuchi and Pinga (2017), acknowledged the disadvantages to include: deficiency in the use of institution's facilities, conflict with property owners, inadequate involvement in extracurricular activities and exposure to cult-

related activities. The disadvantages associated with off-campus residence make students and their parents apprehensive of off-campus residence (Devi et al., 2015).

2.2 Influencers of Students' Choice of Residence

Influencer according to Cambridge Dictionary is that which affects or changes the way people behave. Therefore, factors that influenced students in making choice of residence are termed influencers. Studies have shown that students' choice of residence are influenced by some factors. Kolawole and Boluwatife (2016), identified the influencers as proximity to campus, rent, dwelling types, and facilities provided. Mahama et al. (2016) stated that factors such as accommodation charges, security, water and electricity supply, proximity to lecture halls, and privacy are key. In addition, Kobue *et al.* (2017) submitted that availability of laundry rooms, internet services, secure parks, architectural design, computer labs, unavailability of hostel accommodation, gymnasium, individuals' recommendation, study rooms and number of occupants per room influence students' decision with respect to where to reside. Also, Ibrahim and Musa (2017) acknowledged that shortage of hostel accommodation, proximity to institution, lack of privacy and parents/guardians' decision influence students' choice of residence. Extant literature summarised the influencer to include: location, facilities, quality of services, quality of environment, number of students per room, security, rules and regulation, privacy, quality maintenance, room arrangement, ventilation, access to internet, empathy, culture, common lounge, kitchen, social status. safety, rental value, facilities available, proximity to lecture halls, privacy, infusion of water and electricity cost into rent, gender-based accommodation, and freedom, cleanliness, university's accommodation policy and peer's influence (Adama et al., 2018; Tuan, 2018; Tumer *et al.*, 2019; Armah & Armah, 2021; Du-Plessis & Amoah, 2021). Several influencers of student's choice of residence are identified in literature but for the purpose of this study the influencers will be summarised to comprise: proximity to lecture halls, cost of accommodation, security, privacy, hygienic environment, availability of quality facilities/services, neighborhood/environmental attributes, rules and regulations governing a place and characteristics/aesthetic of the building.

2.3 Measures for Making On-Campus Residence Students' Preference

The state of repair and quality of facilities available in on-campus students' accommodations is integral to making them students' preference. Literature provide various measures in which institutions can adopt to make on-campus residence attractive to students. Shortage of students' hostel accommodations for instance is a major problem in educational institutions in Nigeria (Yunus et al., 2018). Addressing this problem according to Azeez et al. (2016), and Ohaeri and Omorojor (2020) requires allocation of funds for provision of more hostels to deal with the issue of overcrowding, and create more space for students to reside on-campus. Provision of more hostel facilities according to Armah and Armah (2021), may entail measures like institutions partnering with private investors. This disposition is affirmed by Akpeli (2019), who submitted that such partnership will ameliorate the deficit in hostels' infrastructures.

Effective maintenance and management practice are important measures that keep facilities in good condition and improves comfortability of occupants (Agyekum et al., 2016). Adoption of effective maintenance and management practice in hostel facilities will allow for routine inspection to identify potential facilities problem and fixing them before they arise, and facilitates frequent waste disposal, regular water and electricity supply, clean environment among others

(Ofide et al., 2015). According to Igbinedion (2012), having hostels facilities in good condition demands that students are cautious and non-destructives in handling hostel facilities. In the light of this, he recommended measure like enacting and enforcing laws that make students responsible for repair or replacement of damaged facility caused by them. In agreement, Ezeigwenewa and Egolum (2020) suggested provision of regulations for proper maintenance of hostel facilities. Effective maintenance and management of hostel facilities is premised on the experience and expertise of the persons managing hostels. Therefore, the state of hostel facilities is a function of who manages them. In this regard, Okorie and Chima (2020), recommended that hostels facilities be managed by experienced experts with the right technical know-how. In underscoring the importance of effective maintenance and management practice in hostel, Osei-Poku, (2020), opined that adopting effective maintenance and management practice in hostel facilities will make them more attractive to students.

Improved security measure to guarantee safety is very key to making on-campus hostels preferable (Nimako & Bondinuba, 2012). To improve security on campus, institutions are encouraged to employ systematic approaches, utilizing security personnel and adequately communicate information regarding security threats on time (Diamini & Olanrewaju, 2021). In addition, Owusu et al. (2016), stated that institutions should effectively light areas around hostels that are prone to attacks and station security agents in such locations and take other necessary measures to ensure secured campus. Renovation of existing hostels to suite students' taste make them appealing to students. Osei-Poku et al. (2020), reckoned the need to plan and effect renovations of hostels in order to provide conducive residence for students. Also, Igbinedion (2012) is of the view that students' hostels should be made suitable and well furnished with sufficient facilities and adequate services. In the same vein, the quality of facilities and services provided in accommodation correlates with the comfort and convenience of the occupants. According to Suki and Chowdhury (2015), and Ghani and Suleiman (2016), provision of quality facilities and services improve students' satisfaction with accommodation. Similarly, Xu et al. (2020) posited that internet services especially, is of importance to students because it aids study, entertainment and social interactions. Given the degree of importance students placed on internet services, Mahama et al. (2016), recommended that provision of quality facilities and services for on-campus hostels should be at pace with students' population growth. In a nut shell, adequate supply of quality facilities and services will make on-campus hostel students' preference.

Summarily, measures to employ in making on-campus residence students' preference on the basis of literature include: improve internet connectivity, provision of more hostels with supporting facilities in proportion to students' population, effective maintenance and management practice, checking overcrowding, partnership with private investors in provision of more hostel facilities, engagement of experts in management of hostels facilities, regular water and electricity supply, checking vandalisation of hostels facilities, improved security, provision of regulation and policy for hostels management, and renovation of existing hostels to reflect modern design with well-furnished facilities.

3.0 Research Method

Quantitative research design in which questionnaires were used for data collection was adopted for this study. The questionnaire was designed with four sections comprising close-ended questions. The first section focused on demography of respondents, second section addressed place of students' residence, third section is about influencers of students' choice of residence and the

fourth section addressed measures for making on-campus residence students' preference. To determine the relative importance of the influencers as well as measures for making on-campus hostels preferable to students, questions in the third and fourth sections were designed using a scale of 1 to 5. Where: 1 means 'not important', 2 means 'slightly importance', 3 means 'neutral', 4 means 'important' and 5 mean 'very important'.

Undergraduate students are used as the study population, the justification for this choice is predicated on the fact that they constitute majority of the university students' population and major occupants of hostels accommodations. The undergraduate population according to the university record as at the time of this study was 34,606. A representative sample size of 395 was determined using Taro Yamane formula. An internet-mediated approach involving the use of WhatsApp platform was adopted for the administration of questionnaire. Google form was used to create the questionnaire, and the link was sent to various departmental WhatsApp platforms of undergraduate students. The rationale for the use of internet is attributed to the advantages of large audience coverage at lesser time and cost, and convenience of use (Cleave, 2023). 401 responses were obtained from the exercise. Because the 401 responses were correct and complete, the entire 401 responses which is slightly above the representative sample size of 395 were analysed to obtain results of the study. In essence, the sample size of 401 is an adequate representation of the study population.

Relative importance index (RII) values was used for the ranking variables, where more than one variable has the same RII values, standard deviation (SD) value is used to determine the rank such variables. This is done in agreement with the assertion of Field (2005), which stated that variable with the smallest SD value be ranked first, in the instance of tie scores of assessed variables. Since the study used RII values in its ranking, the computed SD is not displayed. Kruskal Wallis test is used to compare the responses of the respondents to establish whether there be significant statistical difference in the ranking of the assessed variables by the respondents. The rationale for the use of Kruskal Wallis test is that, as a non-parametric technique its result has the advantage of minimal error (Garth, 2008).

4.0 Results and Discussion

4.1 Respondents' Demography

The respondents constitute undergraduate of students of the University of Jos, 45.6% of them reside on-campus while 54.4% reside off-campus. 56.9% are males and 43.1% are females. They cut across all levels of the undergraduate programs, with 100 level, 200 level, 300 level, 400 level, and 500 level constituting 3.3%, 10.7%, 19.5%, 44%, and 22.5% respectively. With regards to their marital status, 96.7% of the respondents are single while 3.3% are married.

4.2 Students' Residence Preference

Students' preference of residence is shown in Table 1. A total of 187 of the respondents, representing 46.7% of the sample size preferred on-campus residence while 53.3% denoting 214 of the respondents preferred off-campus residence. This implies that majority of the students preferred off-campus residence to on-campus residence. This finding differs from the finding of

Nwanekezie and Mendie (2019), which posited that most students preferred on-campus residence to off-campus residence in order to reduce cost and possible distractions from studies.

Table 1: Response to Where Students would reside if given a Choice

Place of residence	Frequency	Percentage (%)	Cumulative Percentage (%)
On-Campus	187	46.7	46.7
Off-Campus	214	53.3	100
Total	401	100	

Source: Field Survey, 2024

Table 2 presents the reasons that informed students’ preference of on-campus residence and the percentage distribution of the responses. 44.7% of the respondents preferred on-campus residence because of easy access to institution’s facilities while 27% for the reason of availability of water and electricity and 8.8% for low cost of accommodation, and more. From table 2, it can be inferred that easy access to institution’s facilities, availability of water and electricity, and low cost of accommodation are very important influencers in students’ choice of on-campus residence. The finding agrees with the finding of Tuan (2018), that access to facilities and quality services are second and third most influential factors on students’ decision with regard to place of residence. It also agrees with Kamal *et al.* (2019), who asserted that students seek cheaper accommodation in order to save cost. Similarly, Adama *et al.* (2018) and Tumer *et al.* (2019) in ranking influencers of students’ decision in order of importance, ranked cost of accommodation, and water and electricity, first and second respectively.

Table 2: Reasons for Students’ choice of On-Campus Residence

Reasons	Frequency	Percentage (%)	Cumulative Percentage (%)
Easy access to institution’s facilities	84	44.7	44.7
Availability of water and electricity	51	27	71.7
Low cost of accommodation	16	8.8	80.5
Closeness to course mates/lecturers	13	7.1	87.6
The ambience of the on-campus hostels	11	5.9	93.5
Availability of security personnel	12	6.5	100
Total	187	100	

Source: Field Survey, 2024

Table 3 captured the reasons for the preference of off-campus residence with percentage distribution of the responses. Out of the 214 respondents that opted for off-campus residence, 8.2% of them chose off-campus residence for the reason of availability of water and electricity, 70.1% for the reason of Privacy/comfort/convenience and 9.3% for the reason of better sanitary condition, and more. Among the reasons specified for preference of off-campus residence, Privacy/comfort/convenience has the frequency of 70.1% which is by wide margin higher than the

others. The implication is that majority of the students reside off-campus because of the need for privacy, comfort and convenience. This finding agrees with the position of Adebisi et al. (2017) that privacy is paramount to students when choosing a place to reside. Ibrahim and Musa (2017), also acknowledged the importance privacy to students in making choice of accommodation. The finding that students prefer off-campus residence ‘to avoid moving out of an accommodation at the end of every session’ has not been established in literature as factor influencing students’ choice of residence. Therefore, “not having to move out of accommodation at the end of every session” is a new finding and an addition to the existing established influencers of students’ choice of residence.

Table 3: Reasons for Students’ Choice of Off-Campus Residence

Reasons	Frequency	Percentage (%)	Cumulative Percentage (%)
Availability of water and electricity	17	8.2	8.2
Privacy/comfort/convenience	150	70.1	78.3
The sanitary condition of the place	20	9.3	87.6
Not having to move out at the end of every session	8	3.6	91.2
The nature of the environment	19	8.8	100
Total	214	100	

Source: Field Survey, 2024

4.3 Influencers of Students’ Choice of Residence

Table 4 shows the ranking of the influencers of students’ choice of residence in the order of their relative importance and significance. With the relative importance index in the range of 0.90 to 0.70 and ranks from 1st to 9th. The value of level of significance of each influencer is shown ranging from 0.000 to 0.781. It can be observed that all the influencers have significant influence on students’ choice of residence except neighborhood/environmental attributes, characteristics/aesthetics of the building, and rules and regulations. The implication is that, six influencers: security, hygiene, quality facilities and services, proximity to lecture halls, privacy, and accommodation cost are significant to the students’ choice of residence, however, security, hygiene and quality facilities and services, proximity to lecture hall are of greater influence. Influencers such as neighborhood and environmental attributes, characteristics/aesthetics of the building, and rules and regulations of the place are of insignificant to the students’ choice of residence. The finding that security is a major influencer agrees with the finding of Du-Plessis and Amoah (2021), which states that security is of utmost importance to students in determining place of residence. It also affirmed the position of Tuan (2018), that students consider the presence of security personnel and measures available to check insecurity in making choice of residence. Furthermore, having hygiene as second most important influencer aligned with the assertion of Konadu (2021) that cleanliness is paramount to students in selecting place of residence. Availability of quality facilities and services being among the significant influencers correlates

with Armah and Armah (2021) observation, which stated that absence of quality facilities can make students to reject place of residence. Similarly, the significance of proximity to lectures venue to students’ choice of residence was underscored by Mahama et al. (2016) in their study on modeling satisfaction factors that predict students choice of private hostels. By implication, the issues of security, hygiene, availability of quality facilities/services, and proximity to lectures venue should be prioritized in development of students’ hostels.

Table 4: Ranking of Factors Influencing Students’ Choice of Place of Residence in order of Importance

Variables	Kruska I Wallis Test				
	RII	Rank	Chi-square	Sig.	Decision
Security	0.90	1 st	33.654	.000	Accepted
Hygienic Environment	0.88	2 nd	25.955	.000	Accepted
Availability quality facilities & services	0.84	3 rd	17.967	.001	Accepted
Proximity to lecture halls	0.83	4 th	16.268	.003	Accepted
Cost of accommodation	0.82	6 th	10.184	.037	Accepted
Privacy	0.82	5 th	15.058	.005	Accepted
Neighborhood/environmental Attributes	0.80	7 th	5.498	.240	Rejected
Characteristics/aesthetics of the building	0.73	8 th	2.613	.625	Rejected
Rules and regulations applied	0.70	9 th	2.093	.781	Rejected

Source: Field Survey, 2024

P-value < 0.05

4.4 Making On-Campus Residence Preferable

Measures to adopt to make on-campus residence preferable to all students are presented in Table 5, showing their rank in order of their relative importance and level of significance. The index ranging from 0.94 to 0.80 and ranked from 1st to 9th, and values of level of significance in the range of 0.000 to 0.137. The findings shown that eight measures: regular water and electricity supply, effective security measures, renovation of existing hostels, effective management and maintenance practice, avoiding overcrowding of space, provision of more hostels, modern design hostels with well furnished facilities, and efficient internet connectivity are significant in making on-campus hostels students’ preference. However, the four topmost significant measures are regular water and electricity supply, effective security measures, renovation of existing hostels, and effective management and maintenance practice. Measures like management of hostel by qualified and experienced experts, effective vigilance to check vandalism and illicit behaviours, and partnership with private sector are not of significance to the students.

The finding that regular water and electricity supply constitute the most important measure for making on-campus residence students preference conformed with the submission of Ogunyemi (2022) that irregular electricity and water supply is a major problem of students in on-campus hostels. Having effective security measures in the second position, attest to the fact that students

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are very intentional when it comes to security. Nimako and Bondinuba (2012) submitted that, effective security measures are key to students' safety. Besides the measures ranked in order of their importance and significance, other measures identified in the study include: giving students the option to retain accommodation without having to move to a different one at the end of each academic session; hostel design and facilities should be inclusive of disabled or physically challenged persons.

Table 5: Ranking of Measures of making On-Campus Residence Students' Preference in order of Importance

Variables	Kruskal Wallis Test				
	RII	Rank	Chi-square	Sig.	Decision
Regular supply water & electricity	0.94	1 st	39.945	.000	Accepted
Effective security measures	0.93	2 nd	24.106	.000	Accepted
Renovation of existing hostels	0.93	3 rd	23.088	.000	Accepted
Effective maintenance & management practice	0.92	4 th	17.904	.001	Accepted
Avoid overcrowding of space	0.91	5 th	14.084	.007	Accepted
Provision of more hostels	0.90	6 th	13.811	.008	Accepted
Modern design hostel with well-furnished facilities	0.90	7 th	11.122	.025	Accepted
Efficient internet connectivity	0.89	8 th	10.224	.037	Accepted
Hostels managed by qualified & experienced experts	0.88	10 th	7.054	.133	Rejected
Effective vigilance to check vandalism	0.88	11 th	7.012	.135	Rejected
Partnership with private sectors	0.80	12 th	6.978	.137	Rejected

Source: Field Survey, 2024

P-value < 0.05

5 Conclusion

Hostel accommodation is a vital component of educational institutions in which administrators of institutions should make adequate provision for. Failure of public institutions administrators in the country to provide adequate accommodations for students in the face of rapid growth in students' population has created a forced choice between on-campus and off-campus residence on students. Students that can access on-campus reside off-campus. University of Jos has many of its students residing off-campus. Given the insecurity challenges of incessant religious crisis and kidnapping

cases of which the students have fallen victims, it necessary identify the influencers of students' choice of residence and measures that can be adopted to make on-campus residence their preference, in order to encourage students residing on-campus.

Findings shown that 45.6% of the students reside on-campus while 54.4% reside off-campus. 46.7% of students preferred on-campus residence for reasons of having easy access to institution's facilities, availability of water and electricity, low cost of accommodation, being close to course mates, ambience of the on-campus hostels, and security. 53.3% preferred off-campus residences for the reason of privacy, comfort, convenience, better sanitary condition, and to avoid leaving an accommodation at the end of every session. Six factors consisting of security, hygiene, availability of quality facilities and services, proximity to lecture halls, privacy, and cost of accommodation have significant influence on students' choice of residence, however, security, hygiene, availability of quality facilities and services, proximity to lecture venues are of greater influence. The factor 'avoiding leaving an accommodation at the end of every session' has not been established in literature prior to this study. It is therefore new, and constitute an additional knowledge to the established factors influencing students' choice of residence. Measures comprising regular supply water and electricity supply, effective security measures, renovation of existing hostels, effective management and maintenance practice, avoiding overcrowding of space, provision of more hostels, modern design hostels with well furnished facilities, and availability of efficient internet connectivity, are identified to have significant effect in making on-campus hostels preferable. But the four topmost significant measures are regular water and electricity supply, effective security measures, renovation of existing hostels, and effective management and maintenance practice.

From the established results of the study, to make on-campus hostel preferable to students, it is recommended that efficient security measures that guarantee students safety as well as effective management and maintenance practice that ensure hygienic and conducive environment, with provision of quality facilities and services be prioritised in students on-campus hostels. Also, allocation of number of students per room should be within the carrying capacity of the space to avoid overcrowding and allows for some level of privacy, comfort and convenience. Concerted efforts should be employed through some form of partnership arrangement with private sector to provide adequate on-campus hostel facilities.

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